

DETERMINATION OF PHENOLOGICAL, MORPHOLOGICAL AND POMOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ‘ERKENCE’ OLIVE CLONES

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ABSTRACT. The trial was carried out between 2024-2025 at the Department of Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Ege University. This study aimed to assess ‘Erkence’ clonal variability, describe phenological, morphological and pomological characteristics and to identify superior clones based on yield and quality characteristics. The study was planned with three replicates and each replicate consisted of one tree. According to the results of the study; full blooming of the clones occurred between April 20-24, end of blooming between April 27 - May 2 and fruit ripening between June 26 - September 9, average shoot length was 34.04-69.07 cm, inflorescence length was 2.99-4.25 cm, fruit weight was 2.82-6.03 g, fruit width was 1.54-1.90 cm and fruit length was 2.07-2.83 cm, flesh/stone ratio was 2.71-4.62% and dry matter content was 20.37-45.83%. In line with all these data, it was determined by principal component analysis that fruit and shoot length were the most important distinguishing characteristics.

Keywords: *Olea europaea*, ‘Erkence’, clone, quality characteristics, yield

INTRODUCTION

Olive, one of the oldest cultivated plants in the world, is known as *Olea europaea* L. species of the genus *Olea* of the Oleaceae family [1]. It is a fruit species that plays an important role in the agricultural sector of Mediterranean countries and has a high economic value. It is important for health due to its high nutritional value, table and oil consumption. In addition, its production is increasing due to its high adaptability to environmental conditions [2]. According to 2023 data, 17.3 million tons of olives are produced on 11.1 million hectares. Turkey ranks fourth in olive production after Italy [3].

Olive cultivation has thousands of years of history. Accordingly, many varieties have emerged in different countries. Today, it is estimated that there are more than 2000 olive varieties. Although some of these are known all over the world, some of them are local varieties grown only in certain areas [4]. On the other hand, changes in fruit and tree characteristics occur due to maintenance work and ecological differences. This situation causes the same variety to be recognized by different names [5].

It is important to identify superior clones suitable for different breeding purposes by evaluating the variation among cultivars. In this context, clonal selection is the most widely used method for developing new varieties [6]. Because clonal selection is important for this species. In olive growing countries, it is necessary to carry out clonal selection studies both to prevent variety degeneration and to select types that are superior to the main variety [7]. This allows the identification of genotypes with productivity, resistance to biotic and abiotic stress conditions, non-periodicity, balance of flesh and stone ratio and superior table and oil properties.

The 'Erkence' olive variety is not a variety that has been studied much. It has been the subject of researches in order to compare different quality characteristics among varieties [8]. Canözer [9] explained the physiological, morphological and pomological characteristics of 'Erkence' in his "Catalog of Standard Olive Varieties" study, and Tutar [8] determined the different types that have occurred over time in the 'Erkence' olive variety, which is widely grown around İzmir between 2006-2010, and determined the inflorescence length, number of flowers; leaf width, length, petiole length and petiole thickness; fruit width, length and weight; stone width, length and weight; and morphological and pomological characteristics of flowers, leaves and fruits. This variety is grown mainly in Urla, Seferihisar, Çeşme and Karaburun districts of İzmir province. Selected types from the 'Erkence' population in these locations were protected in the collection parcel of Ege University Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Horticulture. These clones constituted the material of the study. In this project, it is aimed to determine the superior clones in terms of phenological, morphological, pomological characteristics and yield of the selected clones.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

This study was conducted in the clone selection plot of Ege University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Horticulture between 2024-2025 and 'Erkence' olive cultivar was used as material. Different clones of the variety were identified by screening the olive groves in the districts of Karaburun, Çeşme, Urla, Seferihisar, Menderes, Güzelbahçe and Foça and 36 types were planted in 2014 according to the random plots experimental design with 3 replicates of each type. Figure 1 shows the general view of the clone selection plot where the study was conducted. Foliar fertilizer, regular cultural practices and drip irrigation were applied throughout the study.

'Erkence' is an early olive variety originating from İzmir, known as İzmir oil olive, local oil olive or date olive. It is generally evaluated as oil. Its yield is at medium level. It is highly resistant to *Verticillium* wilt [10]. Twig sweetening is a naturally occurring phenomenon that is extremely important for the variety. It has been reported that the cause of this condition is due to the fungus named *Phoma oleae* [11].

Within the scope of the study, 10 'Erkence' olive clones with superior genotypes among 36 clones were selected as material in this study in line with the selection criteria established by considering different characteristics.

Fig. 1. View of the clone selection plot

Methods

Phenological observations

The following phenological observations were made in the study [12]. The date on which the inflorescences reach 2-3 mm in length, the beginning of inflorescence; the date on which an average of 5% of the flowers begin to open, the beginning of blooming; the date on which 80% of the flowers open, full blooming; the date on which the flower petals and almost all of the non-fruiting flowers fall off, the end of blooming; the date when the grains were green and of normal size was recorded as the beginning of green ripening; the date when the peel color started to change from yellow to pink was recorded as the beginning of pink ripening and finally the date when the peel color was black or dark purple was recorded as the black ripening period. Fig. 2 shows the phenological periods of 'Erkence' olive respectively.

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Fig. 2. Photographs of phenological periods in 'Erkence' olive (a: Beginning of inflorescence, b: Beginning of blooming, c: Full blooming, d: End of blooming, e: Beginning of green ripening, f: Beginning of pink ripening, g: Black ripening period)

Morphological measurements

Shoot length was measured with a tape measure and diameter was measured with a digital caliper on four developing shoots from different directions (north, south, east and west) of each tree. Inflorescence length, width; leaf length, width and petiole length were measured in cm with a ruler on 10 randomly selected samples from each tree. The number of flowers was also counted during the measurement.

Pomological measurements

Ten fruit samples harvested in October and taken from each repetition were brought to the laboratory of Ege University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Horticulture for quality analyses. Fruit width, length and stone width, length were measured with a digital caliper sensitive to 0.01 mm and average fruit and stone weight were weighed with an electronic balance sensitive to 0.01 g. Total yield per tree was determined. The fleshy parts of the stone-extracted samples were weighed and the flesh/stone ratio was calculated by proportioning to the stone weight, and the dry matter content was calculated by drying in an oven at 105 °C. The data obtained as a result of observations and measurements were subjected to analysis of variance using SPSS 21.0 statistical package program, and the differences between clones were revealed by Duncan test ($P \leq 0.05$). In addition, all characteristics were analyzed using Pearson correlation and principal component analysis methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In 2024, the data on phenological observations of the 'Erkence' clones are shown in Figures 3 and 4. According to the observations made, the first beginning of inflorescence was observed on March 22 in clone 8 and the last on March 27 in clone 31. The number of days from the beginning of inflorescence to the beginning of blooming varies between 20-25 days. When the blooming period, which includes the beginning of blooming, full blooming and the end of blooming is evaluated, the blooming period, which started between April 13-18, continued for about 15 days and ended between April 27 and May 2. The earliest beginning of blooming was on April 13 in clone 16 and clone 36, and the latest on April 18 in clone 29. Clone 36 was the clone that completed the blooming period in the shortest time. After the end of the blooming period and the beginning of the fruiting period, about 64 days passed until the green ripening

period and the green ripening period started in clone 13 at the earliest on June 26 and in clone 16 at the latest on July 8. Thus, the fruit ripening period, which started between June 26 and July 8, continued for an average of 62 more days and ended in the black ripening period between August 28 and September 9.

Thus, the blooming periods of the clones selected in line with the results obtained in this study started earlier than the dates of May 13 - June 9 indicated by Canözer [9] for 'Erkence' variety and the results of the study carried out by Tutar [8] on this variety.

The genetic characteristics of the clones, the distance of the field to the sea and the structure of the soil are effective on blooming time [8]. Another effective factor is the year. Blooming period and duration may vary according to the climatic conditions during the year [13].

Fig. 3. Blooming period of the 'Erkence' clones

Fig. 4. Fruit ripening period of the 'Erkence' clones

The results of morphological measurements of the 'Erkençe' clones are given in Table 1. Accordingly, it was determined that the differences between the clones were statistically significant ($P \leq 0.05$) in terms of shoot length, diameter; inflorescence length, width, number of flowers, leaf length and petiole length, while there was no difference in leaf width values. When the data were analyzed, the average shoot length of the clones varied between 34.04 and 69.07 cm and the general average shoot length was 41.16 cm. Clone 8 had the longest shoot length (69.07 cm) and clone 28 had the shortest shoot length (34.04 cm). In proportion to shoot length, clone 8 had the highest shoot diameter (0.63 cm). When shoot diameter was taken into consideration, it was determined that the values varied between 0.33-0.63 cm and clone 30 had the lowest value (0.33 cm). The general average shoot diameter was also 0.42 cm.

When the number of flowers in the inflorescence was analyzed, the average number of flowers varied between 9.70 and 18.23 and it was observed that clone 16 had the highest number of flowers (18.23) and clone 31 had the lowest number of flowers (9.70). The general average number of flowers (12.77) was higher than the average number of flowers (11) reported by Canözler [9]. Tutar [8] determined the average number of flowers in the inflorescence as 12.4.

In terms of inflorescence length and width, clone 8 had the longest average inflorescence length (4.25 cm) and clone 31 had the longest average inflorescence width (2.04 cm), with length values varied between 2.99-4.25 cm and width values between 1.05-2.04 cm. Considering that the standard average inflorescence length is 2 cm and varies between 1.4-2.8 cm; it is seen that all clones in the study have a value above this interval and average [9]. Tutar [8] also reported the average inflorescence length as 2.35 cm in his study.

Finally, leaf length and petiole length data are examined; the clones with the longest leaf length and petiole length are clone 8 (6.52 cm) and clone 16 (0.56 cm), while the shortest clones are clone 18 (4.15 cm) and clone 36 (0.39 cm). The average leaf length and petiole length of the clones selected in the study were 4.80 cm and 0.46 cm, respectively. These values are higher than the standard leaf length (4.56 cm) and petiole length (0.32 cm) [9]. In Tutar's study [8], these values were 6.23 cm for leaf length and 0.51 cm for petiole length. According to the results of the study, the average number of flowers, inflorescence, leaf and petiole length values were higher than the values reported by Canözler and Tutar.

Table 1. Morphological characteristics of the 'Erkençe' clones

Clones	Shoot length (cm)	Shoot diameter (cm)	Number of flowers (piece)	Inflorescence length (cm)	Inflorescence width (cm)	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	Petiole length (cm)
8	69.07 a	0.63 a	17.30 a	4.25 a	1.38 b	6.52 a	1.21 ^{ns}	0.50 ab
13	41.26 b	0.36 bc	12.56 b	3.21 de	1.06 b	4.16 e	1.14	0.44 bc
16	39.73 b	0.47 b	18.23 a	3.14 de	1.22 b	5.18 b	1.11	0.56 a
18	39.54 b	0.42 bc	12.26 b	3.43 cde	1.05 b	4.15 e	1.11	0.50 ab
28	34.04 b	0.37 bc	9.93 b	3.31 cde	1.13 b	4.35 de	1.11	0.43 bc
29	35.18 b	0.40 bc	11.80 b	3.42 cde	1.24 b	4.81 bcd	1.13	0.45 bc
30	36.78 b	0.33 c	11.60 b	3.80 abc	1.85 a	5.01 bc	1.20	0.46 bc
31	37.12 b	0.44 bc	9.70 b	4.08 ab	2.04 a	4.52 cde	1.16	0.43 bc
35	38.56 b	0.41 bc	12.83 b	3.61 bcd	1.40 b	4.92 bcd	1.15	0.44 bc
36	40.36 b	0.41 bc	11.46 b	2.99 e	1.29 b	4.38 de	1.03	0.39 c
Avg.	41.16	0.42	12.77	3.52	1.37	4.80	1.14	0.46

Differences between the averages in each row were determined by Duncan's test at $P \leq 0.05$. ^{ns}: Not significant

The results of pomological measurements and yield values of the 'Erkençe' clones are given in Table 2. Accordingly, it was determined that the differences between the clones were statistically significant ($P \leq 0.05$) in terms of fruit width, length, weight; stone width, length, weight, flesh/stone ratio and dry matter content, while there was no difference according to yield values. When the measurement results were analyzed, the average fruit weights of the clones varied between 2.82 and 6.03 g and the general average fruit weight was 4.41 g. Clone

28 had the highest weight value (6.03 g) and clone 16 had the lowest value (2.82 g). The highest and lowest fruit width and length values were obtained in clone 28 and clone 16 in relation to weight. It seems that the values of fruit weight, width and length are higher than the average values of fruit weight (3.04 g), width (1.59 cm) and length (2.21 cm) reported by Canözer [9]. In addition, the average fruit width and length values of Erkence olives harvested with conventional and organic cultivation techniques in Urla Bademler village for 3 years in 3 harvest years and 2 different harvest periods (early and middle) were 1.69 and 2.49 cm in organic cultivation and 1.59 and 2.39 cm in conventional cultivation, respectively [14]. In clone selection studies on olive or other fruit species, there is a great variation in fruit size among the clones. According to Fanizza [15], stone width and length are characteristics with high heritability and these characteristics are affected by environmental conditions very little [16]. Fruit weight is one of the characteristics that attracts the most attention and is evaluated as a selection criterion [17].

Considering stone weight, width and length, clone 28 had the highest stone weight (1.20 g), width (0.82 cm) and length (2.06 cm), clone 8 had the lowest stone weight (0.62 g) and width (0.74 cm) and clone 16 had the lowest stone length (1.58 cm). The average stone weight was 0.62-1.20 g, the width was 0.74-0.82 cm and the length was 1.58-2.06 cm. These values are more superior than the standard stone weight (0.42 g), width (0.71 cm) and length (1.43 cm) values [9]. Although stone weight varies depending on the size of the fruit, the variation may not always be proportional since fruit size can also be affected by external factors [8]. When the stone weights obtained in this study are compared with the fruit weights, it is seen that the two characteristics are not very correlated.

Stone ratio is a desirable value to be low in table varieties. In years with low yields, as the fruits can grow larger, the stones become smaller and the flesh/stone ratio increases [18]. High flesh/stone ratio is a desirable characteristic that may vary among cultivars [19]. In terms of flesh/stone ratio, clone 30 and clone 16 had the highest and the lowest flesh/stone ratio with 4.62% and 2.71%, respectively. When the values are analyzed, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the clones at the statistical significance level. The general average flesh/stone ratio (3.60) is not consistent with the standard flesh/stone ratio (6.23) reported by Canözer [9]. This is due to the fact that the average stone weight of the clones is much higher than the standard stone weight value.

When the dry matter content was analyzed, it was observed that the values varied between 20.37%-45.83%, with clone 36 having the highest ratio (45.83%) and clone 8 having the lowest ratio (20.37%). In this study, it was determined that the general average dry matter content (37.28%) was higher than the standard dry matter content (20.64%) determined for 'Erkence' [9]. The dry matter content of all clones except clone 8 was higher than the standard value.

In a previous study, average fruit weight was 3.26 g, stone weight was 0.52 g and dry matter content was 28.19% [8]. In line with these explanations, in a similar study conducted in different ecologies in 'Erkence' olive cultivar, different findings were obtained in terms of the characteristics examined. This may be due to differences in location, age of the tree and environmental conditions.

The correlation between the examined characteristics of the 'Erkence' clones are shown in Table 3. Fruit width was positively correlated with fruit length ($r=0.866$; $p<0.01$) and stone width ($r=0.390$; $p<0.05$) and negatively correlated with shoot diameter ($r=-0.417$; $p<0.05$) and leaf length ($r=-0.580$; $p<0.01$). The highest correlation was found between fruit weight and fruit width ($r=0.907$; $p<0.01$).

Table 2. Fruit characteristics and yield of the 'Erkençe' clones

Clones	Fruit weight (g)	Fruit width (cm)	Fruit length (cm)	Stone weight (g)	Stone width (cm)	Stone length (cm)	Flesh/stone ratio (%)	Dry matter content (%)	Yield (kg/tree)
8	3.26 f	1.64 d	2.46 c	0.62 e	0.74 e	1.75 bc	4.02 ab	20.37 f	6.03 ^{ns}
13	4.48 cd	1.80 b	2.42 c	0.88 bcd	0.78 bcd	1.59 d	3.77 bc	43.2 b	0.23
16	2.82 g	1.54 e	2.07 d	0.71 de	0.78 bcd	1.58 d	2.71 e	33.43 de	16.7
18	5.23 b	1.88 a	2.65 b	0.97 bc	0.79 abc	1.75 bc	4.08 ab	35.61 d	1.7
28	6.03 a	1.90 a	2.83 a	1.2 a	0.82 a	2.06 a	3.72 bc	33.27 e	1.36
29	4.19 de	1.71 cd	2.45 c	0.99 abc	0.77 cd	1.74 c	3.44 bcd	40.33 c	8.36
30	4.77 c	1.77 bc	2.61 b	0.81 cde	0.76 de	1.84 b	4.62 a	34.73 de	8.36
31	4.71 c	1.76 bc	2.47 c	1.05 ab	0.80 ab	1.74 c	3.21 cde	40.85 c	1.4
35	4.09 e	1.70 cd	2.38 c	0.87 bcd	0.80 ab	1.72 c	3.5 bcd	45.19 ab	5.06
36	4.51 cd	1.72 bc	2.48 c	1.08 ab	0.81 a	1.77 bc	2.88 de	45.83 a	2.73
Avg.	4.41	1.74	2.48	0.92	0.78	1.75	3.60	37.28	5.19

Differences between the averages in each row were determined by Duncan's test at $P \leq 0.05$. ^{ns}: Not significant

Fruit width and length were positively correlated with fruit weight ($r=0.907$ and $r=0.860$; $p<0.01$), flesh/stone ratio ($r=0.362$ and $r=0.456$; $p<0.05$), stone length ($r=0.581$ and $r=0.844$; $p<0.01$) and stone weight ($r=0.624$ and $r=0.551$; $p<0.01$) and negatively correlated with yield ($r=-0.457$ and $r=-0.374$; $p<0.05$), number of flowers ($r=-0.737$ and $r=-0.623$; $p<0.01$) and petiole length ($r=-0.390$ and $r=-0.416$; $p<0.05$). The number of flowers was positively correlated with yield ($r=0.474$; $p<0.01$). In summary, as the number of flowers increases, yield increases but fruit size decreases. Fruit weight was positively correlated with stone width, length and weight ($r=0.500$, $r=0.715$, $r=0.753$; $p<0.01$); yield ($r=-0.444$; $p<0.05$), shoot length and diameter ($r=-0.501$ and $r=-0.510$; $p<0.01$), number of flowers ($r=-0.734$; $p<0.01$), leaf length ($r=-0.622$; $p<0.01$) and petiole length ($r=-0.456$; $p<0.05$) were negatively correlated. Stone width and weight were negatively correlated with flesh/stone ratio ($r=-0.423$ and $r=-0.369$; $p<0.05$) and positively correlated with dry matter content ($r=0.550$; $p<0.01$ and $r=0.448$; $p<0.05$). On the other hand, there were negative correlations between dry matter content with shoot length and diameter ($r=-0.661$ and $r=-0.527$; $p<0.01$), number of flowers ($r=-0.460$; $p<0.05$), inflorescence, leaf and petiole length ($r=-0.430$; $p<0.05$, $r=-0.686$ and $r=-0.484$; $p<0.01$). Stone weight was positively correlated with stone width and length ($r=0.666$ and $r=0.546$; $p<0.01$) and negatively correlated with number of flowers and petiole length ($r=-0.692$ and $r=-0.511$; $p<0.01$). The number of flowers was negatively correlated with stone width and length ($r=-0.481$; $p<0.01$ and $r=-0.439$; $p<0.05$). Shoot diameter was positively correlated with shoot length. Shoot length was negatively correlated with stone width. In addition, shoot length and diameter were positively correlated with number of flowers ($r=0.545$ and $r=0.504$; $p<0.01$) and negatively correlated with stone weight ($r=-0.565$; $p<0.01$ and $r=-0.407$; $p<0.05$). In short, as the number of flowers increases in relation to shoot length and diameter, the yield will increase and the increase in yield will decrease the stone width, length and weight. Inflorescence length was positively correlated with inflorescence width ($r=0.654$; $p<0.01$), leaf length ($r=0.524$; $p<0.01$), shoot length and diameter ($r=0.479$; $p<0.01$ and $r=0.399$; $p<0.05$) and negatively correlated with stone width ($r=-0.402$; $p<0.05$). Leaf length was positively correlated with leaf width ($r=0.442$; $p<0.05$), shoot length and diameter ($r=0.789$ and $r=0.586$; $p<0.01$) and number of flowers ($r=0.626$; $p<0.01$) and negatively correlated with stone width and weight ($r=-0.625$ and $r=-0.627$; $p<0.01$). Finally, petiole length was positively correlated with number of flowers ($r=0.597$; $p<0.01$) and leaf length and width ($r=0.482$; $p<0.01$ and $r=0.366$; $p<0.05$) and negatively correlated with stone width ($r=-0.418$; $p<0.05$)

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficients between characteristics

	FWd	FL	FW	FS	DM	SWd	SL	SW	Y	ShL	ShD	NF	IL	IWd	LL	LWd
FL	0.866**															
FW	0.907**	0.860**														
FS	0.362*	0.456*	0.292													
DM	0.174	-0.105	0.24	-0.357												
SWd	0.390*	0.22	0.500**	-0.423*	0.550**											
SL	0.581**	0.844**	0.715**	0.255	-0.201	0.286										
SW	0.624**	0.551**	0.753**	-0.369*	0.448*	0.666**	0.546**									
Y	-0.457*	-0.374*	-0.444*	-0.167	-0.127	-0.088	-0.185	-0.335								
ShL	-0.36	-0.163	-0.501**	0.171	-0.661**	-0.489**	-0.184	-0.565**	0.122							
ShD	-0.417*	-0.238	-0.510**	-0.115	-0.527**	-0.299	-0.15	-0.407*	0.157	0.739**						
NF	-0.737**	-0.623**	-0.734**	-0.087	-0.460*	-0.481**	-0.439*	-0.692**	0.474**	0.545**	0.504**					
IL	-0.151	0.051	-0.119	0.344	-0.430*	-0.402*	0.069	-0.295	0.131	0.479**	0.399*	0.246				
IWd	-0.123	-0.017	-0.034	0.04	0.027	-0.154	0.066	-0.038	0.075	-0.018	-0.002	-0.085	0.654**			
LL	-0.580**	-0.306	-0.622**	0.154	-0.686**	-0.625**	-0.096	-0.627**	0.288	0.789**	0.586**	0.626**	0.524**	0.198		
LWd	0.057	0.018	-0.118	0.222	-0.245	-0.351	-0.059	-0.21	-0.077	0.297	0.172	0.063	0.307	0.238	0.442*	
PL	-0.390*	-0.416*	-0.456*	0.082	-0.484**	-0.418*	-0.316	-0.511**	0.325	0.267	0.175	0.597**	0.021	-0.225	0.482**	0.366*

Abbreviations: FWd: Fruit width; FL: Fruit length; FW: Fruit weight; FS: Flesh/stone ratio; DM: Dry matter content; SWd: Stone width; SL: Stone length; SW: Stone weight; Y: Yield; ShL: Shoot length; ShD: Shoot diameter; NF: Number of flowers; IL: Inflorescence length; IWd: Inflorescence width; LL: Leaf length; LWd: Leaf width; PL: Petiole length. *: p<0.05 **: p<0.01

In the evaluation made according to the principal component analysis, the principal components, eigenvalues, variation, cumulative variation and the 4 principal component axis and their factor coefficients that emerged when the 17 characteristics examined were taken into consideration are explained in Table 4. These principal components constituted 89.395% of the total variation. In short, the four principal components caused an average of 90% variation when the examined characteristics were considered. The fact that the eigenvalues in the principal components are more than 1 indicates that the weight values of these axes are reliable [20]. The similarities of the quality characteristics based on principal component analysis with each other are shown in the rotated space plot in Figure 5. PC 1, PC 2, PC 3 and PC 4 explain 48.205%, 23.22%, 9.869% and 8.101% of the total variance respectively. With the rotated factor matrix shown in Table 4, the analysis can be better explained and meaningful factors can be obtained. The matrix shows the correlation between the original variable and its factor. Under which factor a variable has the largest weight in absolute value, that variable is closely related to that factor [21]. In principal component analysis, if the weight value of the characteristics in the principal components is above 0.5, it is considered to be quite good. Accordingly, Table 4 shows the 4 factors (PC) and the weights of each variable under the factors (factor weights, correlation coefficient between variables and factors). According to the table, fruit length variable received the highest weight under principal component 1 (-0.956). Likewise, fruit weight, fruit width, yield, number of flowers, stone length, stone weight and petiole length constitute PC 1. On the other hand, flesh/stone ratio, stone width and leaf width constitute PC 2. Under component 2, flesh/stone ratio has the highest weight. PC 3 is constituted by inflorescence width and length characteristics, with inflorescence width having the highest weight. The last component, PC 4, represents shoot length, diameter, leaf length and dry matter content. Under this factor, shoot length had the highest weight of 0.956.

In the evaluation of principal component analysis, when the variation in all parameters examined in the 'Erkence' olive variety is taken into account, the factors with the highest weight are fruit length and shoot length. These characteristics stand out as important distinguishing parameters. In addition to these two parameters, fruit weight, fruit width and shoot diameter were also determined to be the most important characteristics. Thus, it became possible to determine the distinguishing parameters in the data group with the principal component analysis method [22].

Table 4. *Principal component analysis*

Characteristics	PC 1	PC 2	PC 3	PC 4
Fruit length	-0.956	0.206	-0.039	-0.206
Fruit weight	-0.945	-0.056	0.059	-0.576
Fruit width	-0.923	0.071	0.085	-0.488
Yield	0.819	0.246	0.106	0.222
Number of flowers	0.818	0.313	0.243	0.701
Stone length	-0.797	0.093	-0.035	-0.105
Stone weight	-0.76	-0.549	0.167	-0.65
Petiole length	0.652	0.578	0.223	0.436
Flesh/stone ratio	-0.419	0.829	-0.275	0.091
Stone width	-0.454	-0.763	0.299	-0.592
Leaf width	0.152	0.731	-0.674	0.48
Inflorescence width	0.000	0.037	-0.918	-0.009
Inflorescence length	-0.052	0.438	-0.82	0.563
Shoot length	0.259	0.335	-0.15	0.956
Shoot diameter	0.396	0.096	-0.095	0.951
Leaf length	0.483	0.438	-0.32	0.893
Dry matter content	-0.115	-0.683	0.03	-0.8
Eigenvalue	8.195	3.947	1.678	1.377

Proportion (%)	48.205	23.22	9.869	8.101
Cumulative (%)	48.205	71.425	81.294	89.395

Extraction method: Principal component (PC) analysis. Rotation method: Oblimin with Kaiser normalization.

Fig. 5. Similarity of quality characteristics based on principal component analysis with each other in rotated space plot

Cluster analysis was used to determine the degree of similarity among the ‘Erkence’ clones and is shown on the dendrogram in Figure 6. Clones 8 and 16 were separated from the group in which the other clones were together. The clones in the groups were similar in terms of the characteristics examined.

Fig. 6. Hierarchical cluster analysis dendrogram obtained by Ward’s clustering method

CONCLUSION

Our country, which is one of the leading producer countries in terms of the number of olive trees and the amount of production, has an important potential in this field in the world, and especially the 'Erkence' olive variety, which grows intensively in the Karaburun Peninsula of İzmir, has attracted attention due to some of its unique characteristics. However, not much studies have been conducted on the 'Erkence' variety today. The studies that have been carried out are aimed at comparing the quality parameters among the varieties. In this study, phenological, morphological and pomological characteristics and yield levels of clones of 'Erkence' cultivar were determined and 10 clones with superior genotypes were compared among these clones in the clone selection plot of Ege University Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Horticulture for 1 year. Accordingly, clone 36 completed the blooming and fruit ripening period in the shortest time; fruit width and length were correlated with fruit weight, with the highest values in clone 28 and the lowest values in clone 16; fruit length and shoot length were the most important distinguishing characteristics, but fruit weight, fruit width and shoot diameter were also important characteristics besides these two parameters. In addition, cluster analysis showed that clones 8 and 16 were separated from the group of other clones. As a result, it is thought that the comparison of the findings obtained from these selected superior clones will gain importance in terms of olive genetic diversity and breeding studies in the future and it is hoped that it will shed light on both producers and breeders.

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